

Ethnic variation in stated recycling attitudes and behaviors among households in Ontario, Canada

Dr. Calvin Lakhan*

Department of Environment and Urban Change, York University, Toronto, Ontario

Abstract

In a review of 12 ethnic groups in three urban communities in the Greater Toronto Area, this study found that there is significant behavioral heterogeneity with respect to why people recycle, motivators for recycling, and general attitudes towards the environment and stewardship. White Canadians reported having the most positive attitudes towards recycling and awareness of recycling consequences, while ethnic minorities did not readily equate recycling with particular environmental outcomes (i.e. recycling helps mitigate climate change). A particularly salient finding is that there is a marked difference in reported behavior and attitudes between first and second (and third etc.) generation immigrants across all cultural groups. 2nd and 3rd generation Ontarians have much more homogenous behavioral drivers that inform recycling participation relative to those born outside the country. 2nd and 3rd generation Canadians were more likely to report recycling for altruistic and habitual reasons. However, first generation immigrants often reported having significantly different drivers of behavior.

Key Words: Race, Ethnicity, Recycling, Waste Management

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1.0 Introduction

If I posed the question, "Why do you recycle?" to a group of my peers, I imagine most of the answers would be centered around "It's good for the environment, It promotes sustainability etc."

Most recycling promotion and education has tended to emphasize this messaging - the "Feel good" message of recycling is the cornerstone of most engagement strategies, particularly those employed by municipalities. While a rich body of literature exists that explore the linkages between attitudes and recycling behaviour, what remains slightly less clear is whether we all recycle for the same reasons. The "feel good" message of recycling resonates with individuals who understand recycling's potential role in promoting environmental sustainability and stewardship. However, would the same message affect an individual who has never participated in

a recycling initiative before, or does not understand the link between action (recycling) and outcome (stewardship)? Of particular interest, do different demographic groups have different "motivators" for recycling behaviour relative to one another?

This question has become increasingly top of mind for policy planners in both Ontario, and abroad, as a burgeoning increase in immigration has rapidly changed the "face" of the province's recycler. Visible minorities currently make up 25.9% of the province's total population, a figure which has almost doubled between 2001 and 2011[1]. How these changes in the province's overall population affect recycling rates is poorly understood, but there is preliminary evidence to suggest that ethnic minority recyclers face significant barriers (both behavioral and structural) to participating in recycling initiatives. These impediments may, in

part, explain the province's struggle in increasing overall recycling rates for residential recycling programs, which have actually begun to trend downward over the past three years. In response to this, many provincial municipalities have "doubled down" on their efforts to promote recycling initiatives to new Canadians, emphasizing the 3R mantra ("reduce, reuse, and recycle") that has been so successful in the past.

While earlier research examining the efficacy of recycling promotion and education in promoting diversion have been mixed, [2] study examining ethnic minority response to conventional methods of engagement (newspapers, signs etc.) showed that these mediums did not influence stated recycling behaviour, or levels of awareness. A subsequent study examining how religious institutions could be utilized in disseminating P&E materials showed promising results – it was observed that religious groups were demonstrably more effective in promoting recycling behavior among ethnic minorities [3]. However, despite these revealing findings, it raised more questions than answers: Could a "faith based" model of recycling promotion and education be replicated across cultural groups? How should recycling P&E be designed/delivered? Why does the "feel good" message of recycling affects certain groups (and not others) and what forms should promotion and education take depending on the target audience?

It is with these questions in mind that this study was conceived. This study examines ethnic variation in stated recycling beliefs and behaviors among Ontario's 12 largest ethnic groups. Using data collected over a three month period from Ontario's three largest municipalities, this study seeks to examine self reported levels of:

1. Current Recycling Behavior
2. Recycling Attitudes
3. Social and Individual Norms
4. Situational Factors
5. Levels of Perceived Control
6. Awareness or Recycling Consequences

This was done to determine whether there is an observed behavioural heterogeneity among ethnic groups with respect to recycling behaviour, and whether this behavioural heterogeneity manifests itself as having different motivators and attitude attachments towards recycling. The potential need for alternative engagement strategies and recommendations for municipal waste planners are also considered.

Understanding why people recycle, and whether different ethnic groups have different drivers of recycling behaviour will be a critical issue for policy planners as they are forced to adapt the "feel good" message to engage and encourage new Ontarians to participate in household recycling programs.

2.0 Literature Review

There is a relative paucity of literature that specifically examines the role of race and ethnicity as antecedents to recycling behavior. This may be in part due to the sensitivity of attempting to explain behavior using racial and ethnographic variables. Particularly with a topic such as recycling, where participation is seen as a pro social activity, explaining differences in behavior along racial/ethnic lines may leave some groups vulnerable to criticism or abuse. With this in mind, there have been studies that have attempted to expand the existing literature on the profiles of recyclers to include racial and ethnic dimensions. Perry and Williams (2007) specifically examine recycling behavior of ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom. Of note, this study found that variation in attitudes towards the environment and stated recycling behavior exist among ethnic groups, with certain minority groups (namely British Indians) expressing higher levels of recycling participation (despite lower levels of stated environmental concern) relative to the "white" British community (Perry and Williams, 2007). This is in direct contrast to the findings by Williams and Kelly (2003), which found that black and ethnic minority groups are less likely to recycle when compared to white Britonians. Perry and Williams (2007) also found that ethnic minorities felt that they were not being

effectively engaged by the local authority (municipalities). Interview results from the study suggest that recycling participation among ethnic minorities could be encouraged by increasing household awareness about "what you can put in the box" and "increasing the frequency of recyclable collection" (Perry and Williams, 2007). Study participants also expressed a desire for the local authority to communicate information in their native language (i.e. Hindi, Gujarati, Italian etc.). Studies by Melosi (1981), Owens et al. (2000), Meneses and Palacio (2005) and Williams and Kelly (2003) have also included racial variables in their examinations of the socio-demographic profiles of recyclers. While these studies were not designed to specifically explore variation in recycling participation among racial groups, the general consensus is that race is a less important predictor of recycling behavior relative to other factors (such as income and education). Furthermore, there tends to be considerable co-linearity among race and other explanatory variables (i.e. race and income, and race and education), so it is often difficult to isolate the effects of race on recycling participation.

Despite the apparent dearth of scholarship examining the role of race/ethnicity and recycling, there is a significant body of work that investigates ethnic and racial variation in environmental belief and behavior. As noted by Whittaker et al. (2005), there have been two theories used to explain racial/ethnic variation in attitudes towards the environment. The first is rooted in socio-economic standing, where in minorities (who are assumed to be less affluent than "whites") prioritize day to day needs over more abstract ideas such as environmental protection/concern (Whittaker et al., 2005). In direct opposition to this view is environmental deprivation theory, which posits that concern for the environment is a direct function of exposure to environmental degradation. Given that minorities often live in communities most impacted by environmental issues, they would express greater levels of environmental concern

(Whittaker et al., 2005). With this in mind, studies exploring variation in environmental concerns and attitudes of ethnic minorities have had varied findings. While early literature (Hauser, 1962) found that Afro-Americans expressed lower levels of environmental concern relative to Caucasian groups, subsequent studies by Newell and Green (1997), Uyeki and Lani (2000), Mohai and Bryant (1998), and Parker and McDonough (1999) found no significant differences in perception of environmental issues among Afro-American and Caucasian groups. Mixed results with respect to conformity in perception and attitudes towards the environment among Latinos were also found in studies examining Latino environmentalism (Cicchetti and Lynch, 1993; Dwyer, 1994). While most of the existing discourse has generally characterized environmental concerns among minority groups as being less than, or at best, equal to, Caucasians, Whittaker et al. (2005) found the opposite to be true. In an analysis of California polling data, there was significant empirical support for growing levels of environmental concern among minority groups.

However, as noted by Johnson et al. (2004), research examining differential environmental beliefs and behavior among immigrating groups is still very much in its conceptual infancy. Despite the interest in understanding ethnic variation in environmental concern, few studies have examined how attitudes and perceptions towards the environment change among immigrant populations. Understanding whether attitudes/concern towards the environment change when ethnic minorities move to a new country is an area that requires additional investigation. Furthermore, identifying whether there are differences in stated levels of environmental concern and perceptions among first and second generation immigrants is also of particular importance. If there are observed differences in environmental concern between first and second generation immigrants, it may point to behavior being a function of "new" cultural assimilation. Conversely, if there is little

variation in stated levels of environmental concern between first and second generation ethnic immigrants, it would suggest to behavior being influenced by retained "old" cultural values. Both Ouellette and Wood (1998) and Bamberg and Möser (2007) have identified the critical role that past behavior plays in informing existing attitudes, intentions and practices. It should be noted that Perry and Williams (2007) found significant differences between the attitudes and participation of first and second generation ethnic minorities with respect to recycling, with the latter expressing greater levels of stated concern for the environment and awareness surrounding recycling initiatives. However, Carr and Williams (1992) found that environmental perception and behavior among Latino groups was a function of the level of acculturation to "white" value systems. Attitudes towards the environment and pro social environmental behavior among second and third generation Latinos was influenced by the practices of their parents/grandparents (Carr and Williams, 1992).

Lakhan's (2015a) study on differences in self-reported recycling behavior between first and second generation South Asians in Ontario, Canada found that there were significant differences in self-reported recycling behavior and stated levels of environmental concern between first and second generation South Asians. Second generation South Asians viewed recycling more favorably, and indicated higher levels of recycling participation, recycling awareness and willingness to respond to recycling promotion and education literature. The study also found that source separation of recyclables was not a common waste management practice in first generation respondents' country of origin. A lack of past participation in recycling programs served as a barrier to recycling behavior, potentially explaining differences in levels of recycling participation between first and second generation South Asians in Ontario. A subsequent study by Lakhan (2016) examining the role of religious

institutions in affecting stated recycling attitudes and behavior found that cultural and religious organizations were demonstrably more effective in promoting recycling initiatives among target groups relative to the municipality (who have traditionally been tasked with the design and delivery of recycling promotion and education efforts).

However, what has been conspicuously absent from the literature is in examining ethnic variation in recycling attitudes and behaviors. Previous investigations have highlighted that conventional means of recycling promotion and education employed by the municipality does not effectively engage visible minority groups (Lakhan, 2015b). There is also evidence to suggest that alternative means of engagement (i.e. promoting recycling programs using cultural and religious organizations) yields positive results with respect to affecting stated recycling behavior and positive attitudes towards the environment (Lakhan, 2016). The logical "next step" in this research is to understand whether there is significant behavioral heterogeneity among ethnic minorities with respect to recycling behavior and motives. Does a Pakistani immigrant recycle for the same reasons as a Chinese immigrant? Can the same strategies be employed to simultaneously promote recycling behavior in both groups?

This is important for two reason 1) Ethnic minorities, particularly in Ontario, recycle at a significantly lower rate than second and third generation Ontarians of Caucasian descent and 2) Municipalities have traditionally employed a "One size fits all" approach to recycling promotion and education that is premised on an appeal to environmental conscience. Is this the most appropriate approach moving forward if the ultimate goal is to engage the burgeoning population of ethnic minorities that now call Ontario home?

3.0 Materials and Methods

3.1 Description of Study Site

Ontario is Canada's most populous province, situated between 41o85' N and 51o28' N and 95o48' W and 74o74' W, with a total land mass of 1,076,395 km². Ontario remains at the forefront of recycling initiatives and legislation, recognized as one of only three provinces in Canada to implement an extended producer responsibility scheme (EPR) for household recyclables. Residential and commercial waste diversion programs exist for MHSW (Material Hazardous or Special Waste), WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronics Equipment), automobile tires, and printed paper and packaging (Blue Box) materials. Stewardship Ontario is the

industry funding organization designated to collect fees on behalf of packaging producers to finance the operation of the Blue Box program.

An estimated 3.2 million Ontarians identify as being a member of a visible minority group. These individuals make up more than half of Canada's total visible minorities. Combined, the three largest minority groups in Ontario as per the Statistics Canada 2011 census were South Asians, Chinese and Black – which account for nearly two thirds of all visible minorities in the province. Figure 1 provides the relative demographic breakdown of visible minorities in Ontario [1]

Figure 1: Visible Minorities in Ontario

3.2 Study Design

Three geographic regions in Southern Ontario were targeted to conduct focus groups sessions. These include the City of Toronto, the Region of Peel (City of Mississauga and City of Brampton) and York Region (City of Markham, City of Vaughan). These groups were selected on the basis that they provide an adequate geographic representation of the province, and are home to more than 2.5 million residents who

identify as being part of a visible minority group (approximately 46% of the total population of the region).

Survey questions were organized into seven main areas: 1) Current Recycling Behavior 2) Recycling attitudes 3) Subjective Norms 4) Moral Norms 5) Situational Factors. 6) Levels of Perceived Control 7) Awareness of Recycling Consequences. Table 1 Describes the Final Survey Statements Used in the Study.

Table 1: List of Survey Statements:

Current Recycling Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I regularly participate in my cities Blue Box recycling program (either weekly or biweekly) • I take my old electronics to the recycling depot • I take my old paint cans and oil canisters to the recycling depot • I recycle items that I consume away from the home • I knowingly put recyclables in the garbage
Recycling Attitudes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling is good/bad • Recycling is useful/waste of time • Recycling makes me feel good • Recycling is responsible/not responsible
Subjective Norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The people that are important to me think I should recycle • The people who are important to me would approve of me recycling • The community thinks that I should recycle • I am legally required to recycle
Moral Norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We should all work together to recycle • I would feel guilty if I didn't recycle • I would recycle if a religious leader told me to • I would recycle because the municipality told me to • I would recycle because a member of my family/kinship network told me to • It is wrong to waste things that can be used again or still has value
Situational Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling takes up too much time • I will be fined if I don't recycle • Recycling bins take up too much space • It is inconvenient for me to bring my recyclables to a depot • Recycling is too complicated • Separating recyclables is too dirty • There isn't enough space in my recycling bin for my recyclables

Levels of perceived control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The municipality does a good job of letting me know about recycling programs in my region • I know what items can be recycled • I know when to recycle • I know where to take my household recyclables • It is easy/difficult for me to participate in my city's recycling program • Recycling takes time
Awareness of Recycling Outcomes/Consequences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling is good for the environment • Recycling helps prevent wasteful behavior • Recycling preserves resources for future generations • Recycling helps prevent climate change • Recycling doesn't make a difference

Questionnaires were pre-tested and refined prior to conducting the official survey. The pre-test allowed for wording refinements and changes to the ordering of the questions. The finalized survey was conducted over a 10 week period beginning in March 2022 and running through May 2022. Teams of two enumerators and one site supervisor were sent to each municipality for a period of four days each, spending six hours at each survey site.

Questionnaire "booths" were set up in spaces with high foot traffic (namely malls, arenas and public commons areas). Enumerators were asked to approach members of the public (in accordance with the study's target demographics), explain who they were and the purpose of the study, and request approximately 10-15 minutes of the participant's time to complete the survey. A mix of convenience and quota sampling was employed to ensure that survey participants reflected the relative proportions of all major ethnic groups in Ontario (both with respect to their country of origin and proportion of first and second generation immigrants). Initially, enumerators included any individuals who identified as being a first generation visible minority and were amenable to

participating in the survey. As the study progressed (and the sample size increased), enumerators were asked to ensure that additional study participants reflected the relative demographic breakdown of all Ontarians, including Caucasian white, and second and third generation immigrants. Survey responses were recorded by hand and later electronically archived and analyzed using Provalis Word Stat, Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word.

Respondents were asked to answer questions using Likert scales. Respondents were read questions and asked to mark their responses on the survey with the assistance of the enumerator. The interview was recorded and later transcribed in full. Teams of two enumerators would administer the survey, one tasked with taking interview/field notes and the other working with respondents to complete the survey. Enumerators were proficient in several languages, allowing the survey to be administered in the language respondents were most comfortable with. A total of 2214 individuals were approached and asked to participate in completing the survey. Of those approached, enumerators managed to successfully complete

795 surveys, for a response rate of 35.9%.¹ Table 2 provides the summary statistics for all survey participants, while table 3 provides the breakdown by ethnic group.

Table 2 below summarizes the relative demographic breakdown of focus group participants.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of all survey participants

Variable	All participants
Median Age	38.6 years
Median Income ¹	\$45,000-\$60,000
Education ²	45.8%
Gender ³	46.7%
First Generation ⁴	66.6%

Table 3: Summary Statistics by Ethnic Group

Ethnicity	Median Age	Median Income	Education	Gender
Indian/Sri Lankan	40.1	\$45,000-\$60,000	50.4%	47.3%
Chinese	38.6	\$45,000-\$60,000	52.6%	42.4%
Black (African/Caribbean)	39.4	\$45,000-\$60,000	41.5%	48.6%
Pakistani/Bangladeshi	38.4	\$45,000-\$60,000	42.3%	49.8%
White - Canadian	41.1	\$45,000-\$60,000	59.8%	49.5%
White – Eastern European	37.1	\$45,000-\$60,000	47.6%	54.3%
Italian	40.5	\$45,000-\$60,000	45.3%	51.4%
Portuguese	40.7	\$45,000-\$60,000	38.4%	48.4%
Filipino	35.4	\$45,000-\$60,000	40.6%	43.6%
Latin American	36.9	\$45,000-\$60,000	58.9%	52.2%
Mixed Race/Other	40.4	\$45,000-\$60,000	46.5%	49.4%

¹Respondents were asked to select from ranges of income that best represents their earnings, not actual values

²Percentage of respondents with college education or higher

³Percentage of respondents who identified as being male (else female)

⁴Percentage of respondents who identified as being a first generation immigrant (born outside of Canada, presently living in Canada)

While all reasonable efforts were taken to ensure a representative sample that approximates the province’s relative demographic breakdown of ethnic minorities, the total number of participants tended to be more heavily weighted towards South Asian and Asian respondents. Members of Ontario’s Latin American and African ethnic groups are underrepresented in this study (relative to their share of the overall population). It should also

be noted that people who are amenable to participating in a survey may be biased towards recycling behavior. This is often difficult to control for, as asking people to participate in a survey on self-reported recycling behavior will almost always elicit a positive response (given the negative connotation associated with non-participation in recycling). Table 4 describes the total number of study participants by ethnic group.

¹ Given the approximately 3.2 million ethnic minorities over the age of 18 living in Ontario, it was estimated that a sample size of 384 participants was required to ensure that the sample was representative (at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error)

Table 4: Ethnic Breakdown of Study Participants

Ethnicity	Number of Participants
Indian/Sri Lankan	107
Chinese	103
Black (African/Caribbean)	74
Pakistani/Bangladeshi	49
White - Canadian	115
White – Eastern European	67
Italian	55
Portuguese	41
Filipino	70
Latin American	34
Mixed Race/Other	80

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Regression results of demographic variables on stated environmental preferences

A regression was performed to ascertain the strength of the relationship between socio-demographic variables such as education, income and age on stated environmental preferences (including the 7 behavioral components described in table 1). As shown in table 5, stated environmental preferences (namely recycling attitudes and awareness of consequences) is a function of education. Income and age were not shown to be statistically significant variables in our tests. It should be noted that these results contravene previous findings from the literature, which has generally found that stated levels of environmental concern and attitudes towards recycling a function of income and age. While the exact reason for this contradiction cannot be readily explained, the clustering of responses among survey participants (particularly with respect to income levels) may obscure potential relationships between behavior and demography.

Table 5: Regression Results

DF = 795

	<i>Current Recycling Behavior</i>	<i>Recycling Attitudes</i>	<i>Subjective Norms</i>	<i>Moral Norms</i>	<i>Situational Factors</i>	<i>Levels of Perceived Control</i>	<i>Awareness of Recycling Outcomes/Consequences</i>
Education	2.13	2.96	0.94	0.78	1.31	1.42	3.31
Income	1.11	0.31	0.46	0.29	0.41	1.21	0.87
Age	0.47	0.69	0.87	0.82	1.25	0.84	1.32
Gender	1.21	0.74	0.57	0.69	0.68	0.84	0.69

4.2 Survey Results

Using a 7 point Likert scale (with 7 = strongly agree and 1 = strongly disagree), Table 6 aggregates scores for respondents who indicated some form of agreement (a score of 4 or higher).

An Anova test was conducted to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in self-reported recycling behavior, intent, attitudes and influences. For all parent behavioral categories, the data was found to be statistically different at the 95% confidence interval.

	Indian/Sri Lankan	Chinese	Black (African/Caribbean)	Pakistani/Bangladeshi	White - Canadian	White – Eastern European	Italian	Portuguese	Filipino	Latin American	Mixed Race/Other	F > Critical
Recycling Intentions												
I regularly participate in my cities Blue Box program	86%	92%	87%	71%	98%	91%	84%	87%	83%	90%	86%	No
I will take my old electronics to the recycling depot	12%	24%	7%	4%	41%	19%	18%	14%	10%	28%	14%	Yes

I will take my old paint cans and oil canisters to the recycling depot	6%	5%	8%	4%	59%	17%	18%	14%	6%	13%	12%	No
I will recycle items that I consume away from the home (in parks, malls etc.)	56%	47%	55%	31%	83%	42%	56%	39%	48%	71%	47%	Yes
I will sometimes knowingly put recyclables in the garbage	75%	75%	67%	74%	41%	69%	62%	71%	79%	54%	72%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	3.29	3.40	3.14	2.58	4.51	3.33	3.33	3.15	3.16	3.58	3.23	Yes
Recycling Attitudes (I think that recycling is...)												
Good/Bad	85%	91%	92%	74%	97%	79%	84%	74%	87%	94%	90%	Yes
Useful/Waste of Time	71%	74%	81%	66%	89%	73%	75%	64%	71%	84%	76%	Yes
Rewarding /Not Rewarding	50%	55%	58%	42%	82%	76%	64%	62%	59%	71%	64%	Yes
Responsible / Not Responsible	79%	73%	80%	58%	94%	82%	67%	70%	64%	88%	73%	Yes
Sensible/ Not Sensible	54%	66%	74%	48%	74%	76%	61%	67%	52%	68%	56%	Yes
Hygienic/Not Hygienic	57%	43%	67%	31%	82%	69%	73%	67%	65%	75%	69%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	4.62	4.69	5.27	3.72	6.04	5.31	4.95	4.71	4.64	5.60	4.99	Yes
Subjective Norms												
Most people who are important to me think that I should engage in recycling	51%	64%	59%	31%	79%	59%	52%	55%	36%	62%	40%	Yes

Most people who are important to me would approve of me recycling	75%	66%	64%	43%	94%	69%	67%	72%	60%	81%	76%	Yes
My extended cultural community thinks that I should recycle	18%	14%	26%	7%	74%	35%	29%	39%	19%	37%	25%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	3.36	3.36	3.48	1.89	5.76	3.80	3.45	3.87	2.68	4.20	3.29	Yes
Moral Norms												
We should all work together to recycle	78%	84%	87%	64%	94%	79%	75%	80%	80%	91%	76%	Yes
I would feel guilty if I didn't recycle	31%	37%	34%	21%	67%	39%	41%	36%	39%	57%	31%	Yes
I would recycle because a religious/community leader told me to	67%	31%	32%	52%	26%	40%	59%	50%	79%	53%	35%	Yes
I would recycle because the municipality told me to	43%	73%	38%	20%	71%	52%	63%	59%	44%	62%	56%	Yes
I would recycle because a member of my family/kinship network told me to	72%	47%	30%	46%	55%	46%	36%	39%	41%	47%	38%	Yes
I am willing to put extra effort into recycling on a regular basis	57%	54%	64%	36%	78%	61%	57%	53%	56%	75%	53%	Yes

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Everybody should share the responsibility to recycle	72%	76%	81%	43%	94%	83%	81%	78%	81%	89%	82%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	4.20	4.02	3.66	2.82	4.85	4.00	4.12	3.95	4.20	4.74	3.71	Yes
Perceived Control												
The municipality does a good job of letting me know about recycling programs in my region	24%	26%	29%	14%	65%	37%	29%	25%	34%	41%	31%	Yes
I know what items can be recycled	54%	47%	76%	33%	70%	41%	46%	44%	55%	71%	44%	Yes
I know when to recycle	84%	81%	79%	69%	94%	84%	81%	77%	71%	86%	79%	Yes
I know where to take my recyclables	31%	56%	60%	20%	82%	68%	63%	70%	55%	67%	64%	Yes
It is easy/difficult for me to participate in recycling programs	55%	61%	73%	35%	79%	60%	65%	73%	58%	71%	55%	Yes
Recycling depots are convenient to get to	12%	10%	8%	5%	35%	14%	15%	20%	13%	17%	15%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	3.03	3.28	3.79	2.05	4.96	3.55	3.49	3.61	3.34	4.12	3.36	Yes
Situational Factors												
I will be fined if I don't recycle	84%	89%	86%	76%	94%	81%	84%	86%	87%	90%	85%	No
Recycling bins take up too much space	75%	77%	72%	73%	44%	71%	69%	74%	54%	75%	66%	Yes
Recycling is too complicated	52%	54%	48%	71%	31%	49%	52%	57%	52%	39%	46%	Yes

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Recycling takes too much time	67%	66%	51%	57%	29%	48%	58%	52%	67%	36%	58%	Yes
There is insufficient space in the recycling bin that the municipality gives me	71%	72%	64%	63%	71%	68%	61%	62%	71%	62%	64%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	4.89	5.01	4.49	4.76	3.77	4.44	4.54	4.63	4.63	4.23	4.47	Yes
Awareness of consequences												
Recycling is good for the environment	84%	91%	94%	68%	96%	81%	85%	74%	84%	93%	81%	No
Recycling helps prevent wasteful behavior	81%	78%	76%	69%	94%	76%	71%	68%	81%	90%	82%	Yes
Recycling preserves resources for future generations	64%	54%	83%	41%	87%	68%	67%	64%	54%	74%	67%	Yes
Recycling helps prevent climate change	32%	29%	40%	25%	74%	54%	49%	52%	42%	56%	44%	Yes
Reduces waste being sent to landfills	74%	79%	82%	62%	94%	88%	81%	82%	74%	89%	78%	Yes
Weighted Average Score	4.69	4.63	5.25	3.71	6.23	5.14	4.94	4.76	4.69	5.63	4.93	Yes

As shown in table 6, statistically significant differences in self reported recycling behavior and attitudes were observed among survey respondents. For all behavioral categories (intent, attitudes, norms, perceived control, situational factors and awareness of recycling consequences), there was statistically significant differences across the entire sample, and within each pair wise comparison (no two groups reported similar responses). This suggests that there is significant behavioral heterogeneity across cultural groups with respect to recycling behavior. The most obvious of these differences tends to manifest itself in perceived measures of control and normative influences – with the greatest disparity in self-reported behavior being reported among white Canadians vs. all other cultural groups. Latino and Black respondents also seemed to indicate more positive attitudes towards the environment and fewer perceived barriers to recycling participation. Results among non-white non Canadians tended to cluster with respect to a lack of perceived control and awareness of recycling consequences. Every cultural group surveyed reported positive attitudes towards recycling and were not principally averse to participation, but a lack of awareness regarding what constituted recycling and where to take them seemed to serve as a behavioral impediment. Almost universally, survey respondents indicated that they were unlikely to take their waste electronics or hazardous waste to a depot. This confirms previous findings from the literature that perceived convenience is a significant predictor of recycling behavior.

Of note, aggregated scores among behavioral categories (shown in table 6) appear to show that different ethnicities have different obstacles (or motives) for recycling behavior. While all groups reported positive attitudes towards recycling, the Pakistani community found perceived barriers to recycling (namely, it is difficult and time consuming) to be far greater than other cultural groups. Lack of awareness regarding recycling consequences among non White Canadian survey respondents highlight the challenges municipalities face in linking the

“action and outcome” of recycling. It would appear that most groups participate due to a perceived legal obligation, and less so for altruistic or environmental reasons. The role of communal or normative influence on recycling behavior is also a finding that necessitates additional investigation – while no cultural group indicated that normative influence was a significant predictor of behavior, Indian and Pakistani communities indicated that they would be much more likely to recycle as a result of communal pressures. Perceived religious obligation (measured as “I would recycle if a religious authority asked me to” was observed to affect behavioral change among Filipino and South Asian groups, but less so for White (both Canadian, and Eastern European) and Asian groups.

While the reader is advised to exercise caution with respect to whether these findings are attributable specifically to differences involving ethnicity, it does provide strong evidence to suggest that recycling behavior (and behavioral antecedents) are not homogeneous. Even for groups sampled from within the same geographic area, and when socio-demographic variables (age, income etc.) are controlled for, there is significant variation in recycling attitudes and behavior across ethnic groups. The implications of these findings are that recycling engagement strategies, particularly those designed by municipalities, need to be revisited, as an appeal to environmental conscience is unlikely to affect meaningful change beyond a limited group of people (who are probably already recycling, i.e. White Canadians).

Despite the challenges associated with developing customized solutions (and the lower relative levels of recycling participation and awareness) among ethnic minorities, recycling is almost always seen as a “positive” activity that people want to get behind. The key is to not only educate these people about the “how and why” of the program, but improve the infrastructure and opportunities that enable them to participate.

A particularly interesting finding is that 2nd and 3rd generation Ontarians have much more homogenous behavioral drivers that inform recycling participation relative to those born outside the country. While some degree of ethnic variation in behavior does exist among 2nd and 3rd generation Ontarians, this group was much more likely to reported more positive attitudes towards the environment and awareness of recycling consequences. However, first generation immigrants often reported having significantly different drivers of behavior – As noted in section above, different ethnic communities have different attitude attachments and motives for participating in recycling. The inevitable question that arises from this is Why? And what can municipalities do to address it?

5.0 Conclusion

In a review of 12 ethnic groups in three urban communities in the Greater Toronto Area, this study found that there is significant behavioral heterogeneity with respect to why people recycle, motivators for recycling, and general attitudes towards the environment and stewardship. White Canadians reported having the most positive attitudes towards recycling and awareness of recycling consequences, while ethnic minorities did not readily equate recycling with particular environmental outcomes (i.e. recycling helps mitigate climate change). A particularly salient finding is that there is a marked difference in reported behavior and attitudes between first and second (and third etc.) generation immigrants across all cultural groups. 2nd and 3rd generation Ontarians have much more homogenous behavioral drivers that inform recycling participation relative to those born outside the country. 2nd and 3rd generation Canadians were more likely to report recycling for altruistic and habitual reasons. However, first generation immigrants often reported having significantly different drivers of behavior.

As noted in section 4, some communities recycle because of a perceived religious obligation, while others are more likely to recycle

as a result of normative pressures (the “shame” factor). These findings now raise the question, “How should municipalities respond?” Catering to the specific needs and behavioral triggers of the diverse population base of Ontario’s ethnic community is neither feasible nor practical. While bespoke solutions would be the ideal solution, municipalities operate in a world of finite budgets and limited resources. The question now becomes how to engage the greatest number of people while incurring the least amount of cost, and as a tangent to that, what does that engagement strategy look like?

A thorough understanding of the motives and barriers to recycling for ethnic minorities in Ontario is critical in ensuring that their participation in recycling schemes is encouraged. Given the changing demography of recycler’s in Ontario, we cannot assume what has worked in the past will continue to work moving forward. Communication, messaging and methods of household engagement need to be updated and refined to reflect. A failure to design policies that are both culturally sensitive and relevant may impede provincial recycling rates, particularly in light of Ontario's rapidly changing demography.

There is an opportunity for the province to adopt new and innovative approaches to recycling promotion and education messaging and delivery. Ontario’s situation is not unique – ethnic minorities are making up an increasingly larger share of urban populations across Canada and in many countries facing similar demographic shifts resulting from immigration. As such, now more than ever, there is a need to “think outside the box” and develop campaigns that communicate the what, when, where and why of recycling in a culturally relevant way. There exist significant barriers in encouraging ethnic minorities to recycle, but there is also a great opportunity to galvanize millions of new Canadians to reduce, reuse and recycle.

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